

Title: Zero Collision Robot [ZCR]

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INTRODUCTION:

The Robots in the present world are all consists of many advanced technologies. But still the robot is unable to take its own decisions. Due to lack of decision making, there occurs collision. The ZCR is a robot collision related project, in which the robot can make decisions depending on the joint movements.

AIM:

To give a permanent solution for robot collisions.

DESCRIPTION:

The Robot collision is a very common issue in the present automated world. As it cannot be avoided, we undertake some safety measures such as Interference Zoning. But still there are many chances of collision of robot or its parts (it may be collision of the arms of the same robot or the collision between two robots).

Even though there exists many collaborative robots, those robots can only detect the collision in advance and can stop the further motion, but cannot take the appropriate measure for it. The concept of Zero Collision Robot is to detect the collision and to take the preventive action for avoiding the accident without any human interference.